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CDA Conducts Regional Training on Fish Hatching, Culture and Management in INRAN, Maradi, Niger Republic

ALSO INSIDE

- CDA Celebrates with PhD, MSc Graduands, Re-affirms Cordial Relationship with Alumni
- VC Inaugurates Reconstituted CDA International Scientific Advisory Board
- CDA Visiting Scholar Shares Experience of his Research Project at Michigan State University, USA

BAYERO UNIVERSITY
KANO

**CENTRE FOR
DRYLAND AGRICULTURE**
AN AFRICA CENTRE OF EXCELLENCE

CENTRE FOR DRYLAND AGRICULTURE

Bayero University, Kano – Nigeria

... an Africa Centre of Excellence

VISION

Resilient and Prosperous African Drylands

MISSION

To improve livelihood, resilience and sustainable use of natural resources in African drylands through training and demand-driven research

CORE VALUES

- Good leadership and Inclusiveness
- Passion and Teamwork
- Commitment and Sacrifice
- Integrity and Transparency
- Professionalism and Excellence

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CDA Conducts Regional Training on Fish Hatching, Culture and Management in INRAN, Maradi, Niger Republic

The Centre for Dryland Agriculture in collaboration with the Institut National De La Recherche Agronomique Du Niger (INRAN), Maradi, Niger Republic conducted a training on fish hatching, culture and management held at CERRA-INRAN, Maradi from 13th to 17th March 2023.

117 women and youth participated with 70% of the beneficiaries being women and 20 students from Dan Dicko Dankoulodo University of Maradi (UDDM).

The facilitators of the training were Musa Usman Aminu and Zahrau Rabiu Mudi from the Department of Fisheries and Aquaculture, Faculty of Agriculture, BUK and Abdussalam Imam Abdullahi from the National Biotechnology Development Agency, Federal Ministry of Science and Technology. It was a 6-day hands-on practical training where participants were taken through theoretical and practical stages of fish spawning, culture, production and management.

The beneficiaries were excited about the training and confident of the possibility of them setting up fish production enterprises.

The CDA Management team led by the Director Prof. J. M. Jibrin facilitated and coordinated the training. Other management members of CDA with the director were the Deputy Director Training, Professor Sanusi Gaya Mohammed and the Deputy Director, Outreach and Publications, Professor Amina Mustapha.

The Director of CERRA, Dr Laouali Mahamane Nasser, in his remarks welcomed the participants and urged them to take full advantage of the rare opportunity brought to their doorstep.

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Cat fish processing during the training

Salting, as a fish preservation method

Washing cat fish for processing

CDA Management Pays Courtesy Visit to Vice Chancellor of Dan Dicko Dankoulodo University Maradi (UDDM)

The CDA Management staff led by the Director, Professor Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin, paid a courtesy visit to the Vice Chancellor of UDDM. The team, which conducted a training in CERRA-INRAN Maradi, used the opportunity to pay the courtesy visit. The aim of the visit was to discuss and strengthen the existing relationship between the partners. The acting Dean of the Faculty of Agriculture, Dr Elhadji Gounga Mahamadou, led the CDA Team to the Vice Chancellor's office.

The Vice Chancellor, Prof Sani Mamane, expressed

his satisfaction with the partnership and commended the CDA in assisting to build the capacity of their staff and students through short-term trainings.

After the courtesy visit, the Acting Dean took the CDA team round the newly established Dean farm at the Faculty of Agriculture in the university. The CDA Director informed the Dean that under the partnership activities with UDDM, CDA would assist the faculty in providing some equipment for the take-off of the newly constructed fishpond and building the capacity of their staff for the successful utilization of the fishpond.

The Vice Chancellor of UDDM, Prof Sani Mamane with Prof J.M. Jibrin at the Centre flagged by the Acting Dean of Agric UDDM and Prof Amina Mustapha on the right while the Deputy Vice Chancellor of UDDM and Prof S.G. Mohammed are on the left

CDA Team with some staff of UDMM at Livestock Unit

Pure Balami breed at Faculty of Agriculture, UDMM

CDA Team with the Acting Dean of UDMM and a staff

The newly constructed fish pond at the Faculty of Agriculture, UDMM

Chairman of Reconstituted CDA International Scientific Advisory Board, Professor Jimmy Adegoke (middle) in a group photograph with the Deputy Vice Chancellor, Research and Development, Prof Abdullahi Sule-Kano (3rd right), Director of CDA, Prof Jibrin M. Jibrin (2nd right), Dr. Ahmed Ali Yakasai (3rd left) and staff of CDA

VC Inaugurates Reconstituted CDA International Scientific Advisory Board

The Vice Chancellor, Professor Sagir Adamu Abbas, inaugurated the reconstituted International Scientific Advisory Board of the Centre for Dryland Agriculture on 27th January, 2023.

The Board, among many other things, is to guide the Centre in designing programmes that are effective and helpful in mitigating the issues of climate change and guide it in achieving synergy of the research agenda in line with the needs of the country and the region at large.

The Vice Chancellor, who was represented by the Deputy Vice Chancellor, Research and Development, Professor Abdullahi Sule-Kano, said the University Management would continue to give the Board all the necessary support to achieve its full potentials.

He said there was a glimmer of hope and enthusiasm that the caliber of professionals of international repute assembled in the Board would further underscore the CDA's pre-eminent position as one of the highly rated Africa centres of excellence making enormous impacts in West and Central Africa.

The Chairman of the Board, Professor Jimmy Adegoke, assured the University Management that the board would leverage on the successes recorded by expanding the Centre's international and regional networks and creating more impacts in the region.

Professor Adegoke on behalf of the members of the Board thanked the University Management for the confidence reposed in them and commended the Vice Chancellor and

the Management for always supporting the CDA.

He said CDA was recognized as one of the top performing centres in Africa and singled out the Director, Professor Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin, whom he described as an incredible leader and a gift to the centre and the university. He also commended the vibrant team members, who have been working round the clock to assist the director.

The Chairman lauded other members of the Board for accepting to serve and said that together they would work assiduously to accomplish the tasks and goals set aside to move the Centre forward.

In his remarks, the Director of the Centre, Professor Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin, briefed the board about CDA's evolution and how it got World Bank grants and the renewal of its ACE project as a result of excellent performances. He also told them about the international accreditation of CDA programmes, research projects, international, regional and local collaborations, as well as regional students given admission from 15 countries.

He said in the current ACE for Impact Project, the World Bank made a mid-term evaluation in June last year and CDA scored 59% which was good and because of that the centre was penciled down for additional funds. He said the Centre had done much more than that now because in the recent progress report towards impact assessment, it scored 5/5 and for its plans for entrepreneurship, 30/30.

Some of the Terms of Reference of the Board are to develop a robust world-class research and development agenda that will address the critical development issues on African drylands and guide the Centre in leveraging the opportunities for research funding from within and outside Africa.

Members of the board are:

Professor jimmy Adegoke – an internationally renowned climate scientist from University of Missouri, Kansas City, USA as Chairman.

Other members are: Professor Yemi Akinbamijo – Executive Director, Forum for Agricultural Research in Africa (FARA); Dr Ramajdita Tabo (ICRISAT Director for West and Central Africa) who is also a joint winner of 2007 Nobel Prize for Peace; Professor Lindsay Stringer (University of Leeds, UK); Professor Gregory S. Jenkins, (Pennsylvania State University, USA); Professor Muhammad Auwal Hussaini (the pioneer Director CDA and Dean

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Faculty of Agriculture, BUK); Dr Ahmed Ali Yakasai, the Director of the Directorate for Laboratory Management and Director CDA, Professor Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin, who serves as secretary. There are three Assistant Secretaries: CDA Deputy Director Training, Professor Sanusi Gaya Mohammed, CDA Deputy Director Outreach and Publications, Professor Amina Mustapha and the CDA Deputy Director of Research, Dr Kabir Mustapha Umar.

CDA Celebrates with PhD, MSc Graduands, Re-affirms Cordial Relationship with Alumni

Director of CDA, Prof Jibrin M. Jibrin (left), CDA staff, faculty members and the graduates eating and rejoicing

The Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) celebrated with its graduands for the 2018/2019 and 2019/2020 academic sessions. A total of 83 PhD's and MSc's graduated from the Centre's supported programmes, out of which 17 were regional students from West and Central Africa.

The Director of CDA, Professor Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin, told the graduands that it was a gathering to congratulate them for being found worthy in character and learning and celebrate the completion of their study. He said they had a responsibility by giving back to the society.

Professor Jibrin added

Dr. Rabou Charifi (left) presenting a plaque to the Director of CDA, Prof Jibrin M. Jibrin (right), on behalf of regional graduates

that the Centre kept track of the progress of its alumni through its strong alumni relationship. He added that the Centre was ready to support their activities, so that the relationship remained

mutually beneficial.

The Deputy Director Outreach and Publications, Professor Amina Mustapha, expressed pleasure with the number of female graduands among them. She said the

centre was proud of their modest achievement, hoping that the knowledge acquired would be judiciously utilized to impact the society.

Amadou Charifi Rabiou, who studied PhD in Natural Resources Management and Climate Change, presented a plaque to the Director CDA, Professor Jibrin on behalf of all the regional students, who graduated from the centre. He said the contribution of the centre on their lives was quite enormous.

Dr. Rabiou, who is also a professional statistical and spatial consultant, expressed gratitude to the Director, Deputy Directors and all other staff of the centre for impacting positively on their lives.

Cross section of the PhD and MSc graduates at the CDA Conference Hall

Our Relationship with CDA will Last Forever

– CDA Alumni

Alumni of the Centre for Dryland Agriculture who graduated at Bayero University's 36th and 37th Combined Convocation ceremonies said that they have completed their studies with a positive impression about the Centre. They said that the centre would forever remain an indelible footprint in their lives.

The graduands, who spoke during a brief but colourful get-together organized by the centre to congratulate them, stated that they benefitted immensely with the world class facilities that aided the smooth conduct of their researches and were grateful to their teachers, who encouraged them throughout their studies.

In his remark, Banyah Dieudonne Shasha, a Cameroun national was full of praises for the centre's significant impact on their study, especially with the support, encouragement, facilities and mentorship received from the centre. He promised that the relationship with the centre would last forever. He said he was highly delighted over how he completed his MSc within two years without any hitches.

Ama Sulaymane Aboubacar from Niger Republic, who studied MSc Natural Resources Management and Climate Change commended the centre for providing all that they needed to fast-track their studies.

Ummi K. Mohammed, who studied PhD Natural Resource Management and Climate Change, said she was completely remodeled with the type of training and engagement from the centre. She said she would give back to the society what she had learnt.

Banyah Dieudonne Shasha, a regional graduate from Cameroun commending the CDA

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Umami K. Mohammed, one of the PhD graduands

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Dr. Zulaiha Dankoli, one of the PhD graduands

CDA Visiting Scholar Shares Experience of his Research Project at Michigan State University, USA

Ashafa Salisu Sambo, a CDA PhD student in Livelihood and Natural Resource Economics, went for a student exchange visit for four months to Michigan State University, USA under the Legume Systems Innovation Lab Project. He shared his experiences on Thursday, 16th February, 2023 at the CDA Conference Room in the presence of the Director CDA, Professor Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin, Dr Hakeem Ajiegbe of ICRISAT, the Deputy Director CDA, Outreach and Publications, Professor Amina Mustapha, staff and the postgraduate students of CDA.

Ashafa Sambo, while in the Michigan State University, had learnt many things, including Data analysis using STATA and how to use Latex/Overleaf software and how to conduct literature review to identify research gaps in the literature.

He said that he was determined to teach and train colleagues on what he had learned on and would be open to students to provide them guidance on how to conduct literature search and review.

While in Michigan State University, Ashafa worked with Dr. Michael Olabisi and Dr. Mywish Maredia.

Ashafa also worked on *Ki Kasuwa Go App*, which is an application that supports the development of a virtual marketplace that users of mobile phones can access across key markets in West Africa.

Staff and students listening to the experience sharing of the visiting scholar

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Research Partners are Dr. Hakeem Ajeigbe of ICRISAT, the Center for Dryland Agriculture, Bayero University, Kano, Nigeria and Dr. Toyin Ajibade of University of Ilorin, while the Technical Partners are Venture Garden Group (VGG), Lagos Nigeria and Dennis Phillips (Dept. of Computer Science – Michigan State University).

From left. Dr. Hakeem Ajiegbe of ICRISAT, Ashafa Salisu Sambo, Prof Jibrin M. Jibrin and Prof Amina Mustapha

CDA Postdoctoral Researcher Selected for Open Doors Fellowship Programme of the International Plant Biotechnology Outreach

An academic Biochemist (Toxinologist)/Medical Laboratory Scientist and a postdoctoral researcher at the Centre for Dryland Agriculture, Bayero University, Kano, Dr Hadiza Lawal Abdullahi has been selected for the 2023 Open Doors Fellowship Program (ODFP).

The programme is designed to support women postdoc researchers in African institutions, sponsored by the International Plant Biotechnology Outreach (VIB-IPBO).

Dr Hadiza Lawal Abdullahi

Inspired by the shortage of female mycotoxicologists in Africa, the African food mycotoxin contamination crisis, and its negative impact on health and economy, she is leading a multidisciplinary research project—the Mycotoxin Research Group of Bayero University and hopes to strengthen mycotoxin research capacity and collaboration, through a research stage at the Centre of Excellence in Mycotoxicology and Public Health (CEMPH), Ghent University, Belgium.

CDA HOLDS 9TH MONTHLY INDUSTRY TALK

The Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) on 28th March, 2023 hosted its 9th Monthly Industry Talk. The guest speaker, Mr Deji Ige, Communications Advisor, Innov8 Hub, Abuja, shared his experience on the topic *Industry Trends and Best Practices in Sustainable Agriculture*.

Addressing the role of industry in sustainable agriculture, the speaker stressed that innovation and technology are essential for advancing sustainable agriculture, ensuring increased efficiency, food security, climate resilience and vibrant value-chain.

Mr Ige shared the Innov8 Hub's experiences in agricultural innovation, including how they help innovators/inventors to transform their ideas into inventions and how they guide

Mr Deji Ige

with prototype development and the transition of prototypes into minimum viable products, as well as connect innovators with investors. They also provide a favourable environment, technology and facilities for people to transform their ideas into innovations and promote

technologies and techniques in line with international best practices.

According to the guest speaker, over 15 agro-ventures had been created and supported with mentoring and guidance of the Hub within a span of 2 years. He encouraged CDA to collaborate with top-notch innovation hubs for technical guidance and support in operating its hub. He applauded CDA for trending the pathway towards a triple-helix paradigm's road for collaboration between the private, public, and academic sectors.

Earlier, the Director, Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA), Professor Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin, said the Centre invited Mr Deji to present the 9th monthly industry talks as part of its continuous effort to bridge the gap between academia and industry.

Director of CDA, Deputy Directors, staff and students listening to the presentation

Director of CDA, Prof Jibrin M. Jibrin (left) and Dr Murtala M. Badamasi

Project Manager, Dr Yusuf Garba right and Deputy Project Manager, Dr M.M Bello

Cross section of the participants listening to the presentation

Desta, an Ethiopian PhD student commenting on the presentation

Research Focus

This study aimed at contributing to the adoption of appropriate agricultural systems in cowpea production in a context of climate change through the use of irrigated crops as an alternative to increase the level of food availability, while integrating methods such as zai technology able to increase water use efficiency at field. The zai also called *Tassa* technic is an ancestral agricultural technique consisting of digging holes of variable dimensions depending on the crop in which sowing is done. It was developed by farmers in the northern Burkina Faso, after the dryness of 1970s (Danjuma & Mohammed, 2015; Partey *et al.*, 2018)

Thus, understanding the relative effect of *zai* and drought stress on growth and yield of cowpea under irrigated conditions is not only important but necessary.

Thiombiano Celestin, a regional student from Burkina Faso conducting his research work at CDA lab

Therefore, studies were carried out in Burkina Faso during the 2020 and 2021 dry seasons at Kamboinsin, in the Environmental and Agricultural Research and Training Centre (CREAF) located at 12°28' N and 01°33' E at 300 m above sea level and at Kouare in the Eastern region at 12°03'36"N and 00°21' 55" E, to assess the effects of zai depth and drought stress on the growth and yield of irrigated cowpea and the effects of zai depth on weed density and striga appearance as well as the profitability of the use of the zai system in cowpea production. The experiments consisted of three zai levels (Tillage (the control), 15 cm and 25 cm depth), three drought stress (control; drought at seedling stage; drought at flowering stage) and four cowpea varieties (Gorom local, Moussa local, KVx396-4-5-2D, Tiligre).

The results showed that drought stress at the flowering stage drastically reduced cowpea pod , grain and haulm yields. Drought at the seedling stage had a minimal effect on grain yield, but substantially increased fodder yield. Zai of 25 cm and 15 cm depth increased cowpea grain yield

by 87% and 50% respectively compared to the control (tillage). KVx396-4-5-2D recorded the highest grain yield per hectare; Moussa local exhibited lower grain yield but recorded the highest haulm yield.

The profitability analysis showed that the highest gross revenue and net revenue were registered in 25 cm zai depth, while lower values were recorded in the control (tillage), mostly in drought stress conditions. However, the highest benefit-cost ratio was consistently recorded in the tillage. This shows that zai technology and zai pit depth variation enable a substantial increase of cowpea grain yield, but do not guarantee an economic high benefit-cost ratio when implementation cost is taken into account. The use of a mechanical method in constructing the zai could reduce the cost and increase the benefit-cost ratio.

Zai technology remains a recommendable agricultural practice for cowpea production, regarding its ability in substantially increasing grain yield, as it can contribute to increase the level of food availability.

